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DEVICE FOR INVESTIGATION OF FLOWS CHARGED PARTICLES AND NEUTRONS

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Abstract

This paper describes a device for studying the fluxes of charged particles and neutrons, which can serve as a harbinger of an approaching earthquake. Based on the results of preliminary experiments, it can be assumed that the change in the fluxes of charged particles and neutrons emitted by nuclear processes is associated with seismic phenomena in the earth's crust. For example, in more than 25 cases of earthquakes in the Asian region with a magnitude above 4, intense changes in the fluxes of charged particles and neutrons were observed 10-12 hours before the events. Strengthening of signals was sometimes observed 2-3 days before the events, and after them, they disappeared, which hints at a possible correlation.

The proposed device can be **used** to study the fluxes of neutrons and charged particles of low energies of the earth's crust in order to identify their relationship with seismic activity.

Keywords: earthquake precursors, forecast, correlation, scintillation sensors, neutron fluxes, charged particle fluxes.

Great efforts are being made all over the world to be able to predict earthquakes, but humanity is often powerless in the face of an unexpected attack by the elements of the earth. The destructive property of all seismic disasters is not only their gigantic energy, which takes away human lives and destroys material and cultural values, but also their suddenness and unpredictability. The problem is complex and requires reliable criteria for assessing seismic hazard. Methods for registering earthquake precursors differ both in the complexity of the algorithms created for early real-time data analysis and in the small amplitudes of the received signals, which are insufficient to create a reliable system for early detection of danger. This is due to the instability of time, the difference in the effects of the distribution of precursors, and the inadequacy of the properties of precursors to earthquake parameters, which calls into question the main goal - early prediction of seismic activity. catastrophe. The currently existing methods for predicting seismic phenomena do not provide comprehensive information in advance. Thus, the United States refused to carry out large-scale forecasting work, and Californian seismologists summarized: "According to the new model, earthquakes are random." There are no generally accepted methods for solving this problem, since epicenters are usually located at a depth of 5–35 km in the bowels of the earth and occupy vast territories that cannot be modeled by

traditional methods [1]. The generalization of experimental data in the existing methods for predicting earthquake precursors is formulated as extremely unreliable observed in various phenomena on the earth's surface, since these geophysical phenomena are not always unambiguously associated with an impending earthquake in a given area, and the use of mathematical methods is unlikely to reduce this uncertainty. The main drawback of the ongoing work on the development of methods for predicting natural disasters is the lack of basic information about the time of the event, the location of the earthquake epicenter and the strength (magnitude) of the impact associated with the low efficiency of registered precursors. There is no scientifically fundamentally substantiated concept of the occurrence of earthquakes for the development of a forecasting method. The problem remains unresolved, there is no sufficiently reliable method for predicting earthquakes of any (short-term, medium-term) time level.

Task: It is necessary to create a device with high efficiency for registering the fluxes of charged particles and neutrons (harbingers) emanating from the epicenter of the upcoming earthquake.

To solve this problem, a device is proposed (Fig. 1), consisting of two layers of scintillation detectors **1** for detecting charged particles, laid by carbon absorbers **5**, and the last row of neutron helium detectors **6**, as well as eight directional detectors arranged around **3**.

Fig. 1. Device for registering earthquake precursors:

a – top view; *b* – front view, sectioned vertically along the central plane parallel to the front wall; $\alpha = 45^\circ$; 1 - scintillation detectors; 2 - PMT; 3 – direction detectors; 4 - PMT; 5 – carbon absorbers; 6 - neutron counters

Plastic scintillation detectors **1** are a single element based on plexiglass, with an added scintillating substance, when charged particles hit, they emit a glow, and PMT **2** glued to the ends of the four corners of the detectors convert this glow into electrical signals. The sum of the signals of all eight PMT **2** is output in one channel. PMT **4**, glued to the centers of the direction detectors **3** - is converted into electrical direction signals in eight channels. The sum of the signals of all 6 neutron counters into one channel. Thus, at the output of the device we have 10 channels of electrical signals.

The device operates in the tracking mode, waiting for the appearance of a flux of neutrons and charged particles that exceed a predetermined detection threshold. When the threshold of charged particles and neutrons, precursors of earthquakes, is exceeded, a glow occurs in the detectors, and PMTs convert these glows into electrical signals. Signals from 10 channels enter the electronic unit, where they are converted into a digital code and registered in the PC database for further analysis and processing.

With an increase in the seismic activity of the region, in the nuclear - radioactive processes in the earth's crust, associated with the deformation of the earth's layers, earthquake precursors are formed, radioactive ionizing particles are released, such as protons, neutrons and alpha particles. The atomic nuclei of the matter of the earth's crust are split in the interaction of these strongly ionizing particles, their interaction with the earth's matter is accompanied by the formation of a nuclear-physical cascade and leads to instantaneous splitting in the volume occupied by the cascade. Splitting processes are especially effective when neutrons are captured by nuclei. Nuclear-radioactive reactions take place, a stream of neutrons and charged particles are born - the harbingers of an earthquake. The fluxes of these ionizing particles increase before earthquakes and are recorded by neutron and scintillation detectors on the earth's surface before an earthquake occurs.

Continuous recording of charged particles and neutron fluxes in chronological order in the database by

the proposed device allows the study of their relationship between earthquakes, the parameters of which are continuously recorded by an international network of seismographs.

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